

Firearms and Suicide Among Hispanic/Latino Adults: Understanding the Challenges and How We Can Help

Firearms are a common and deadly method of suicide.

Our research identified key challenges Hispanic/Latino adults often experience before suicide involving firearms. **Recognizing the following challenges may help loved ones get help for those who are struggling.**

Knowing the challenges Hispanic/Latino adults experience can help save lives in our community. But this is not enough. We must also understand suicide warning signs and work towards prevention.

Scan the following QR code to find more information about:

- **Warning signs.** Suicide warning signs include talking about, planning (such as random goodbye texts, notes, and giving away sentimental items), or researching ways to die.
- **Firearm safety & safe firearm storage.** Creating space and time between a firearm and someone having suicidal thoughts can help save a life.
- **Resources.** National suicide prevention and mental health resources.

People who die by suicide with firearms often face several of these challenges at one time:

HEALTH PROBLEMS AND SUBSTANCE USE

New symptoms or worsening health:

- Mental health conditions might include depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder, or substance use disorder.
- Physical health conditions might occur, including pain, cancer, and chronic illnesses (like diabetes).

Other suicide attempts in the past.

Alcohol or substance use (like marijuana or methamphetamine)

- Especially when using before a suicide attempt to help deal with life stress.

RELATIONSHIP TROUBLES

Anger, sorrow, and/or grief caused by romantic relationship crises (like a breakup).

Intense or high-emotion arguments, especially with romantic partners, before an attempt.

FINANCIAL AND LEGAL DIFFICULTIES

Financial difficulties, including a job loss, unemployment, or needing to work multiple jobs to make ends meet.

Legal difficulties such as court hearings, being accused of a crime, or immigration issues.

ACCESSIBLE FIREARMS

People who die by suicide can get firearms in different ways. Some people buy firearms legally or illegally. Others take or borrow firearms from friends, partners, or family members.

- Handguns are most common.
- Even when firearms are locked up and unloaded at home, someone having suicidal thoughts may still be able to get the firearms.

Dial 9-8-8 at any time if you or a loved one is thinking about suicide or experiencing a crisis.

The 9-8-8 Suicide & Crisis Lifeline is available 24/7 to offer support.